

A comparative study on survival and growth of larvivorous fish, *Rasbora daniconius*, *Puntius ticto* and *Puntius conchonus*

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Abstract : Experiments were carried out on the survival and growth of *Rasbora daniconius*, *Puntius ticto* and *Puntius conchonus*. The motivation of the study was to obtain information for growing the fish on a commercial scale for their use as biological control agents against mosquito larvae. The effects of temperature, total hardness, DO, pH and feed on the growth of fish were also investigated. Excessive value of total hardness was found because very rich calcium ion is present in Chitrakoot area. There was significant increases in growth rates of fish as temperature was increased from 28°C to 30°C. Further increases in temperature up to 32°C, did not further affect growth. The positive and highly significant correlations 0.991488, 0.9581 and 0.9935 were found between length and weight of *P. ticto*, *P. conchonus* and *R. daniconius* respectively. The regression was significant at 5% level of probability.

Keywords : Temperature, Total Hardness, DO, pH, mosquito larvae, indigenous fish

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